

EFFECTS OF LONG TERM TENSION ON KEVLAR ROPES: SOME PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Thomas P. Bourgault

NAVAL UNDERWATER SYSTEMS CENTER
NEWPORT, RI 02840

Abstract

This paper is a summary of the preliminary results obtained thus far in the NUSC Kevlar Test Program. The purpose of the program is to investigate the documented strength reduction of a number of Kevlar ropes when subjected to a variety of loads in the ocean environment.

Long term tests, both in-air and in-sea water were initiated with periodic residual testing to establish the effects of load, time and environment on over 400 rope samples.

Final and more conclusive results will be available upon completion of the 12 month test period in November 1978.

Introduction

At the Oceans 76 Conference, the Naval Underwater Systems Center presented data showing extensive strength loss of Kevlar after four months in an ocean mooring system.¹ At about this same time, the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution produced data supporting these findings which together posed serious questions as to the lifetime and reliability of using Kevlar in the ocean environment.²

Prior to these reports, all documented testing done by DuPont and others on the basic Kevlar fiber showed no significant strength loss when subjected to various load levels both in air and in water. Therefore in an effort to resolve this dilemma, the Naval Underwater Systems Center acquired funding to initiate a comprehensive test program to investigate this phenomena.

This report describes the test program conducted and some preliminary results that indicate no "significant" loss in strength of Kevlar ropes after both the three and six month test periods.

Test Program

After researching all existing information along with the results of various test programs, it was found that the majority of documented data was based on the testing of individual Kevlar fibers and not from finished rope samples.

Another discrepancy in the available data was the lack of actual environmental testing, and before the NUSC and WHOI data became available, there was essentially no at-sea test results. Therefore, in order to undertake a program which was both realistic of actual usage and at the same time controlled for variable isolation, NUSC consulted with DuPont and the rope manufacturers to lay out the entire test plan.³ From these meetings, the following six categories were identified as being the most important considerations in an effort to determine the effects of long term tension on Kevlar ropes.

These considerations include:

- 1) fiber to be used to build the samples,
- 2) rope constructions to be tested,
- 3) duration of the test,
- 4) static load levels,
- 5) environment, and
- 6) terminations to be used.

All Kevlar rope samples acquired for the test program use Kevlar 29 as the basic building component. This fiber was specially fabricated by DuPont for the test program and fully characterized by them prior to shipment to the manufacturers. This not only assured the quality of the fiber to be used in the test program but also established a basis for comparison should the results indicate a basic fiber problem.

Both the NUSC and WHOI data was comparable although the rope constructions (and manufacturers) tested by each were different. Therefore, an effort was made to include in the sample group as many different constructions as was economically feasible. The actual sample groups and rope constructions selected are discussed later in this report.

The duration of the test program is one year with the initial control testing being followed by residual testing at three, six and twelve months. In this way, the time history effect of load on the various samples could be determined.

The static load levels selected were 0, 1200, 2100 and 3000 lbf. All samples were specified at 6000 lbf so that these load levels would correspond to 0, 20, 35 and 50% of the rated breaking strength. In this way, the effect of increasing loads would be

determined along with any aging problem when considering the zero load samples.

The environment itself was an important consideration since most of the fiber testing had been done in air and the NUSC and WHOI data followed extensive exposure at sea. Therefore, to determine any environmental effects, analogous in-air and in-sea water testing was done.

Finally, since general usage ropes are supplied with manufacturers terminations, it was decided to acquire all samples pre-terminated utilizing each manufacturers most effective method. In this way, the cutting and reterminating of long samples which could possibly affect the data during residual testing was eliminated.

Test Samples

The five sample groups included in the test program are defined below:

A. U.S. Steel: 3 x 19 construction, torque balanced oceanographic wire rope with a polyethylene jacket and terminated at both ends with swaged sockets.

B. Philadelphia Resins Corp.: 1500 denier braided construction with a polyester jacket and terminated at both ends with epoxy filled wire rope sockets.

C. Wall Rope Works: 1500 denier uniline (parallel) construction with a polyester jacket and spliced terminations at both ends with heavy thimbles.

D. Cortland Line Co.: 15000 denier counter/helical construction with a polyester jacket and spliced terminations at both ends with thimbles.

E. Cortland Line Co.: 15000 denier braided construction with a polyester jacket and spliced terminations at both ends with thimbles.

The U.S. Steel wire rope samples were included in the test program as an additional control and also as an up-to-date comparison of steel versus Kevlar in similar applications.

The total number of test samples, 400 (80 per sample group) is significant since this translates into 800 individual terminations. Therefore, due to the large number of terminations, the test program becomes an investigation of not only the effects of load etc. on Kevlar but also the reliability of terminations and the ability of the manufacturers to apply them. The breakdown of the 400 samples and the entire test program is given in figure 1.

EXPOSURE LOAD TIME HISTORY	MONTHS				TOTAL NO. OF SAMPLES
	0 (10/77)	3 (1/78)	6 (4/78)	12 (10/78)	
0 LOAD					
-AIR	5	3	3	3	14
-SEA WATER	-	3	3	3	9
1200 lbf					
-AIR	-	3	3	3	9
-SEA WATER	-	3	3	3	9
2100 lbf					
-AIR	-	3	3	3	9
-SEA WATER	-	3	3	3	9
3000 lbf					
-AIR	-	3	3	3	9
-SEA WATER	-	3	3	3	9
					77
					+ 3 SPARES
					80

Figure 1. Test Program and Sample Breakdown

Test Set-Up

Subjecting 400 samples to four separate loads in two different environments was accomplished by attaching the various samples of each group in series for each particular load and exposure time.

In air, the sample lengths were suspended horizontally (anchored at one end) and tensioned by a snatch block arrangement with the prescribed weight.

For the in-water test, steel buoys were fabricated (with the buoyancy of the floats being equal to the required tensions) and used in sub-surface mooring systems in Narragansett Bay. The big advantage of implementing the test in this way is that, at the conclusion of each exposure period complete systems could be recovered and tested without interrupting any other test apparatus.

Test Results

The environmental testing was initiated in October 1977. At the time of this writing, both the three month and six month test periods have been completed with only the twelve month data left to finish the test program.

All the sample testing throughout the program took place at the U.S. Coast Guard R&D Center at Avery Point in Groton, CT. The testing was done by the author and Mr. Carl Jones of DuPont so that any discrepancies or unexpected phenomena could be analyzed when they occurred.

All samples from the various manufacturers were specified at 6000 lbf breaking strength. However the delivered samples ranged from 5000 to 10,500 lbf. Because of this, the expected loading

percentages of 20, 35 and 50% were variable depending upon the sample group.

The tensile testing procedure for all the samples is identical. Each one is exercised from 0 to approximately 1500 lbf ten times prior to destruction. The cross head speed is held constant at 12 in/min. Finally, it should be noted that a 5% change in strength is attributed to scatter which is based on the evaluated standard deviations of all the samples.

The results obtained thus far in the test program are presented in figures 2 thru 6. They are given individually by sample group to avoid confusion when comparing results.

All of the 3000 lbf in-water moorings failed early in the test due to premature sample termination failures. Because of this, and the lack of spare samples, this portion of the program has been deleted.

The steel wire rope, as expected, has lost none of its strength at this point in the program. The lack of in-water data is a result of corrosion which developed due to a galvanic couple between the galvanized terminations and the large bare steel buoys. These samples are being reterminated and the data will be published when available.

ENVIRONMENT	TEST PERIOD (MONTHS)	STATIC LOAD (lbf)	AVERAGE STRENGTH (lbf)	CHANGE IN STRENGTH (%)
AIR	0	0	6926	-
	3	0	7170	+3.5
	6	0	7253	+4.7
	3	1200	7347	+6.1
	6	1200	7293	+5.3
	3	2100	6868	-0.8
	6	2100	7613	+9.9
	3	3000	*	
	6	3000	7387	+6.7
	SEA WATER	3	0	7413
6		0	7107	+2.6
3		1200	*	
6		1200	*	
3		2100	*	
6		2100	*	

* data not yet available

Figure 2. U.S. Steel Wire Rope Results

ENVIRONMENT	TEST PERIOD (MONTHS)	STATIC LOAD (lbf)	AVERAGE STRENGTH (lbf)	CHANGE IN STRENGTH (%)
AIR	0	0	6276	-
	3	0	6293	+0.3
	6	0	6053	-3.6
	3	1200	6347	+1.1
	6	1200	5650	-10.0
	3	2100	5800	-7.6
	6	2100	5867	-6.5
	3	3000	*	
	6	3000	6047	-3.6
	SEA WATER	3	0	5733
6		0	5593	-10.9
3		1200	6060	-3.4
6		1200	5367	-14.5
3		2100	5500	-12.4
6		2100	*	

* data not yet available

Figure 3. Philadelphia Resins Braid Results

The Philadelphia Resins 1500 denier braided Kevlar shows a reduction in strength in virtually all of the tests. However, the tendency of the in-air tests is for the reduction to decrease with increasing load. A possible explanation is that elongation, alignment and load sharing of the fibers is accomplished more efficiently at the higher loads. This argument does not hold true however, for the in-water samples and the absolute numbers are significantly higher which possibly indicates that sea water does contribute to overall strength reduction.

Initially in the test there was some problems with the Philadelphia Resins potted terminations. After some investigation, it was found that the solvent used to clean the Kevlar had not been given sufficient time to evaporate thereby causing inefficient bonding between the fiber and epoxy. (Note: Philadelphia Resins had, for safety purposes changed solvents from MEK to less volatile Xylene. However, because of this problem, they have returned to using MEK exclusively.)

The Wall Rope uniline construction showed much scatter in the data and at this point in the program, no definite trends can be established. The data from the final test period will hopefully yield more insight into this construction.

One very important characteristic was noted however, with the uniline in the 3000 lbf in-air (3 month) set-up. Shortly after this test was initiated, a Philadelphia Resins sample failed (due to the termination/bonding problem noted above) causing all the samples in this string to go slack. The sample was replaced and the weight reapplied but within two days a uniline sample failed midspan. Again the sample was replaced and the test continued. However, this phenomena

occurred four more times and it is now believed that the uniline construction is susceptible to shock damage caused by the instantaneous release of tension. This finding is important when considering a mooring system under load that is recovered by the actuation of an acoustic release which in effect would subject the rope to the same shock release damage as that observed in the test set-up. If this is the case, then reusing the rope could be catastrophic even after extremely short exposure periods.

ENVIRONMENT	TEST PERIOD (MONTHS)	STATIC LOAD (lbf)	AVERAGE STRENGTH (lbf)	CHANGE IN STRENGTH (%)	
AIR	0	0	4946	-	
	3	0	5193	+5.0	
	6	0	5340	+8.0	
	3	1200	4733	-4.3	
	6	1200	4993	+1.0	
	3	2100	4693	-5.1	
	6	2100	4560	-7.8	
	3	3000	*	-	
	6	3000	4400	-10.2	
	SEA WATER	3	0	5140	+3.9
		6	0	5400	+9.2
		3	1200	5173	+4.6
6		1200	4780	-3.4	
3		2100	4625	-6.5	
6		2100	*	-	

* data not yet available

Figure 4. Wall Rope Uniline Results

Cortland Line supplied two different constructions to be evaluated in the test program. The 15000 denier counter helix construction has showed a similar tendency as the Philadelphia Resins data, that being in this case, a decrease in the strength reduction with time under load. Also similar is the greater strength loss observed in sea water for this construction.

As noted previously, the Wall Rope uniline showed no indication of sea water being detrimental. This data reaffirms the fact that sea water does not affect the strength of the Kevlar fiber.^{4, 5} However, this does not exclude the possibility that in some constructions, sea water does have a detrimental effect due to increased fiber abrasion etc. when wet.

ENVIRONMENT	TEST PERIOD (MONTHS)	STATIC LOAD (lbf)	AVERAGE STRENGTH (lbf)	CHANGE IN STRENGTH (%)	
AIR	0	0	7358	-	
	3	0	7680	+4.4	
	6	0	7710	+4.8	
	3	1200	7360	0.0	
	6	1200	7385	+0.3	
	3	2100	6760	-8.1	
	6	2100	7260	-1.3	
	3	3000	*	-	
	6	3000	7380	+0.3	
	SEA WATER	3	0	6987	-5.0
		6	0	6547	-11.0
		3	1200	6680	-9.2
6		1200	7380	+0.3	
3		2100	6708	-8.8	
6		2100	*	-	

* data not yet available

Figure 5. Cortland Counter/Helix Results

The Cortland 15000 denier braid tested performed extremely well in the program with no system failures caused by premature sample or termination problems. However, very little data, as shown in figure 6, could be used to evaluate the overall performance of this rope. The reason for this was that almost all samples failed "within" the termination during residual testing. Therefore, this data did not reflect the actual rope strength and was not accepted as being valid.

ENVIRONMENT	TEST PERIOD (MONTHS)	STATIC LOAD (lbf)	AVERAGE STRENGTH (lbf)	CHANGE IN STRENGTH (%)	
AIR	0	0	10666	-	
	3	0	**	-	
	6	0	**	-	
	3	1200	**	-	
	6	1200	**	-	
	3	2100	**	-	
	6	2100	10380	-2.7	
	3	3000	*	-	
	6	3000	10190	-4.5	
	SEA WATER	3	0	10240	-4.0
		6	0	9660	-9.4
		3	1200	**	-
6		1200	**	-	
3		2100	**	-	
6		2100	*	-	

* data not yet available

** termination failures

Figure 6. Cortland Braid Results

Conclusions

The preliminary results obtained thus far in the test program have provided no definitive trends attributable to all Kevlar ropes. The environmental testing in sea water has been conclusive in that it appears that this medium has little, if any, affect on the basic Kevlar fiber. The effects of load and exposure time have also varied throughout the sample groups which indicates that a major variable affecting residual strength is rope construction. Based on the data generated thus far, this does not appear to be a major factor, however, the final results from the 12 month test period should provide additional insight into the extent of this problem.

The test program has reaffirmed the need for additional termination research and has also uncovered a load release problem with the parallel construction.

References

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